

THE TECHNOLOGY OF EXTRACTING LITHIUM FROM GEOTHERMAL BRINE.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15095893>

Abstract

Geothermal brines are considered a promising source of lithium. This article analyzes lithium extraction technologies, particularly ion exchange resins, membrane filtration, and solvent extraction methods. Additionally, possibilities for improving efficiency and recycling wastewater are examined.

Keywords: lithium extraction, geothermal brines, ion exchange, membrane filtration, solvent extraction

In recent years, the importance of lithium in electrical engineering, the battery industry, and other high-tech sectors has been increasing. Lithium reserves from traditional mines are limited, making the search for alternative sources a pressing issue. Geothermal brines are considered a promising source for industrial-scale lithium extraction, as they contain lithium in relatively high concentrations. This article discusses lithium extraction technologies from geothermal brines, along with their advantages and disadvantages.

The study examines existing scientific articles and industrial practices on lithium extraction from geothermal brines. The following key technological approaches were selected for analysis:

- Ion exchange – lithium extraction using specialized resins;
- Membrane filtration – separation of ions in water through physical barriers;
- Solvent extraction – lithium separation using organic solvents.

The efficiency, energy consumption, and environmental impact of each technology were analyzed.

Ion exchange resins bind lithium ions present in water, allowing for their subsequent extraction using specific reagents. While this method offers high selectivity, the lifespan of ion exchange materials is limited.

Reverse osmosis and nanofiltration technologies are used for lithium extraction. This method is environmentally friendly and allows for water

recycling. However, the rapid fouling of membranes and the high energy demand of the technology are among its drawbacks.

This method involves extracting lithium using organic solvents. While solvent extraction enables the production of highly pure lithium compounds, the use of chemical substances may pose environmental challenges.

Lithium extraction from geothermal brines will remain a key technological direction in the future. The research findings indicate that ion exchange and membrane filtration technologies have advantages in terms of environmental safety and efficiency. Further studies are needed to optimize these methods and improve wastewater recycling processes.

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